

LAURA ELIDEDT RODRIGUEZ¹

EDIBLE NOTIONS

Tasting AI, Food, and the Bias of Perception

ABSTRACT

Edible Notions explores how artificial intelligence reflects and reshapes cultural narratives through food examples. Created during the Summer Sessions residency program in 2024, the project examines biases in AI datasets by training models with contrasting perspectives on biomaterials like avocados, tomatoes, and mushrooms. Through speculative dining and audiovisual elements, the installation invites reflection on how technology perpetuates, distorts, or

challenges food-related histories. By “feeding” both humans and AI, the work highlights the parallels between biological consumption and digital knowledge intake, questioning how perspectives embedded in AI influence our understanding of food, culture, and technology’s role in shaping them.

KEYWORDS: art and science, multimedia installation, AI dataset, food biomaterials, food narratives

¹ Laura Elidedt Rodriguez is a multidisciplinary artist and researcher with expertise in art and molecular biology. Her work explores the intersections of technology, culture, rituals, and perception through bioart and new media. She is a Guest Tutor for Ecology Futures at Avans Hogeschool, an Adjunct Professor of Bioart at ITMO University, and an Invited Artist at Emergence, Delft University.

INTRODUCTION

The paper focuses on describing the creative process of the artwork *Edible Notions* created during the Summer Sessions residency program in 2024 at the Metamedia Association in collaboration with V2_Lab for Unstable Media. The artwork is built upon practices with artificial intelligence and inspired by the biases and perspectives in humans and algorithms. It introduces a methodology to generate tailored small datasets with contrasting perceptions of the same object of study, which in this case are fruits, biomaterials, and cultural stories.

Datasets for image generation with AI are usually large collections of images paired with textual descriptions. These models learn to associate certain visual features with text through various techniques like diffusion models, used in this project. The quality and diversity of these datasets are significantly impacted by the model's performance and the collection of images². It is very difficult to provide unbiased representations due to many factors, including biases in the training data, the model architecture, and the inherent challenges in capturing the complexity of human concepts and experiences into the machine.³

Edible Notions is an installation that explores differential perspectives or bias through the medium of the common biomaterials of our food that have been heavily technologized. Beginning with the premise that perspectives represent our particular attitudes toward the world and shape our relationships with it, this installation prompts a reflection on which perspectives are being overlooked or have evolved over time. This inquiry is especially pertinent as these perspectives are being passed into the emerging technologies that will shape our future. For instance, the perspectives we embed in neural networks of artificial intelligence may perpetuate our biases or introduce diverse interpretations of events and objects.

The artwork explores the biomaterials that create our dishes, taking a deeper look into their inner narratives and cultural and technological stories. It seeks to draw parallels between our biological feed and the mental intake of thoughts, which populate the precarious or vast types of datasets feeding our current artificial intelligence networks. Through a dining experience featuring speculative dishes accompanied by audiovisual elements, the installation invites visitors to reflect on the biases embedded in our food systems and how AI and technology can enhance, reveal, distort, or reshape these narratives. As visitors engage in the act of feeding, they become aware of the digital act of feeding our neural networks.

² Amir Naseh, Jinhee Roh, Emin Bagdasaryan, and Amir Houmansadr, "Injecting Bias in Text-to-Image Models via Composite-Trigger Backdoors," *arXiv preprint*, 2024, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.15213v1>.

³ J. Li, L. Hu, J. Zhang, T. Zheng, H. Zhang, and D. Wang, "Fair Text-to-Image Diffusion via Fair Mapping," *OpenReview*, 2023, <https://openreview.net/forum?id=vDJ4tzczlG>.

CULTURAL BIAS AND AI MISREPRESENTATION

Cultural bias in AI is naturally influenced by its data collection process and the architecture of the algorithms. An overrepresentation of certain groups within many datasets leads to the biased development of algorithms that tend to manifest socially iniquitous results.⁴ For a simplified example, if an AI is trained to recognize a "cat" only in black cat pictures, it might fail to recognize an orange cat because it has learned to link cats with the color black. AI also struggles to understand the cultural meanings attached to symbols. For instance, it might not recognize that black cats can symbolize good fortune in some cultures and bad luck in others. The question remains: who decides what data shapes AI and the meanings it conveys?

Biases in AI are well-documented. Buolamwini and Gebru found that facial recognition systems perform worse on darker-skinned women, largely due to datasets being dominated by images of white males.⁵ Caliskan, Bryson, and Narayanan argue that AI learns implicit biases from human knowledge, such as word associations, which can extend to visual data, affecting AI behavior.⁶ As a female Mexican artist, I have personally faced such misrepresentations. Benjamin, in *Race After Technology*, discusses how emerging technologies, including AI, can deepen social inequalities if they aren't designed inclusively.⁷

AI bias can take diverse forms. First, algorithmic bias occurs when machine learning models unintentionally favor certain outcomes.⁸ Second, data bias happens when datasets don't capture a diverse range of people, skewing AI results toward overrepresented groups.⁹ Third, human bias is introduced during data collection or decision-making, reflecting societal prejudices. Philosophical discussions about technological bias, such as Hui's concept of "cosmotechnics," argue that technology should be understood in its cultural context. He critiques modernization as a way of imposing one worldview.¹⁰ This view warns that unchecked AI could reinforce dominant narratives instead of recognizing cultural

⁴ Batya Friedman, and Helen Nissenbaum, "Bias in Computer Systems." *ACM Transactions on Information Systems* 14, no. 3 (1996): 330–47, <https://doi.org/10.1145/230538.230561>.

⁵ Joy Buolamwini and Timnit Gebru, "Gender Shades: Intersectional Accuracy Disparities in Commercial Gender Classification," *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research* 81 (2018): 1–15, <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v81/buolamwini18a/buolamwini18a.pdf>.

⁶ Aylin Caliskan, Joanna J. Bryson, and Arvind Narayanan, "Semantics Derived Automatically from Language Corpora Contain Human-Like Biases," *Science* 356, no. 6334 (2017): 183–86, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal4230>.

⁷ Ruha Benjamin, *Race After Technology: Abolitionist Tools for the New Jim Code* (Medford, MA: Polity Press, 2019).

⁸ Aylin Caliskan, Joanna J. Bryson, and Arvind Narayanan, "Semantics Derived Automatically from Language Corpora Contain Human-Like Biases," *Science* 356, no. 6334 (2017): 183–86, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal4230>.

⁹ Ninareh Mehrabi, Fred Morstatter, Nripsuta Saxena, Kristina Lerman, and Aram Galstyan, "A Survey on Bias and Fairness in Machine Learning," *ACM Computing Surveys* 54, no. 6 (2021): 1–35, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3457607>.

¹⁰ Yuk Hui, *Art and Cosmotechnics*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2021.

diversity.

The artistic research of *Edible Notions* challenges these biases by intentionally reshaping AI training data to include symbols of traditional knowledge. It questions whether AI should reflect local cultural stories rather than universal values, offering an alternative approach to machine learning that acknowledges cultural diversity.

RESEARCH AND EXPLORATORY CONCEPTS

During the Summer Sessions residency in collaboration with Metamedia (Pula, Croatia) and V2_Lab for the Unstable Media (Rotterdam, Netherlands), I explore methodologies of creating diverse and a more disobedient approach to creating datasets. The name of the project is *Edible Notions*, as I decided to play with the concept of “feeding” the algorithm and feeding our bodies and minds.

The creative outcome could be seen as a human and algorithm collaboration. Donna Haraway argues that the cyborg, a human and machine fusion, can challenge and reinforce dominant ideologies. She sees technology as neither inherently liberatory nor inherently oppressive but actually a site of struggle, and I wanted to showcase this struggle between different contrasting narratives.¹¹ The process of feeding information suggests that technology is not neutral—it reflects and reproduces social relations, but it also offers possibilities for subversion. Therefore, AI reflects the perspectives of its creators, users, and context, a notion called “situated knowledges.”¹² The understanding of this human-AI collaboration requires thinking of the world in terms of the apparatus in constant production.

By adopting this perspective, the research in *Edible Notions* partially challenges the assumption of technological neutrality, where AI acts as a creative partner, merging human narratives with algorithmic processes. Along a similar line of thought, we can find the concepts of Bruno Latour regarding the Actor-Network Theory, which posits that human and non-human entities co-construct social realities, exemplified in the work’s collaborative, cross-entities approach.¹³ By integrating AI into the creative process, *Edible Notions* reflects the Actor-Network Theory premise, presenting AI as an agent actively participating in the co-creation of cultural and social narratives.

Eduardo Kohn, Professor of Anthropology at McGill University, explores the idea that non-human entities—like plants and fungi—participate in the creation of

¹¹ Donna J. Haraway, “A Cyborg Manifesto: Science, Technology, and Socialist-Feminism in the Late Twentieth Century”, in *Simians, Cyborgs, and Women: The Reinvention of Nature* (New York: Routledge, 1991), 149—81.

¹² Donna J. Haraway, “Situated Knowledges: The Science Question in Feminism and the Privilege of Partial Perspective,” *Feminist Studies* 14, no. 3 (1988): 575-99, <https://doi.org/10.2307/3178066>.

¹³ Bruno Latour, *Reassembling the Social: An Introduction to Actor-Network-Theory* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005).

knowledge.¹⁴ This perspective resonates with our research, where common biomaterials (tomatoes, avocados, mushrooms) are not seen merely as passive ingredients but as carriers of cultural and ecological narratives. The artwork prompts us to consider that the natural world contributes actively to the stories and meanings we construct, and when we bring a technological entity such as AI into the creative process, it becomes a team of actors in the construction of knowledge. *Edible Notions* illustrates that what we feed into technology is inherently partial. An artwork using a modified dataset critiques the supposed neutrality of digital systems and emphasizes that local, situated perspectives are essential to understanding and representing our world.

CONTRASTING NARRATIVES IN FOOD

Over two months of experimentation, I created small datasets based on cultural notions of three main fruits/biomaterials that have been heavily technologized in production and have undergone significant shifts in their social perspectives over time.

Avocados: dual narratives and narcotraffic in Mexico

In the recent decade, avocados have become symbols of health and hype culture in Western markets, associated with wellness and vibrant lifestyles. Yet, in Michoacán, Mexico—where I am from—they are a commodity stained by violence. The burst in global demand has attracted drug cartels, leading to extortion and conflict in the area, earning them the nicknames “green gold” and/or “blood avocados.”¹⁵ This contrasting narrative is often overlooked by European culture, while in correlation, there is a rise in community violence and avocado prices in Michoacán.¹⁶ Over more than 20 years, cartels have infiltrated the industry, extorting farmers, packers, and exporters, escalating environmental damage and social instability.¹⁷

¹⁴ Eduardo Kohn, *How Forests Think: Toward an Anthropology Beyond the Human* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2013).

¹⁵ Amanda Erickson, "The Bloody Price of Mexico's Avocados," *The Washington Post*, January 5, 2024.

¹⁶ Romain Le-Cour-Grandmaison, and Paul Frissard-Martinez, *Violent and Vibrant: Mexico's Avocado Boom and Organized Crime* (Brussels: Greens/EFA, 2023), https://www.greens-efa.eu/files/assets/docs/violent_and_vibrant_mexico__s_avocado_boom_and_organized_crime.pdf.

¹⁷ De la Vega-Rivera, Alfonso, and Leticia Merino-Pérez, "Socio-Environmental Impacts of the Avocado Boom in the Meseta Purépecha, Michoacán, Mexico," *Sustainability* 13, no. 13 (2021): 7247. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sul3137247>.

Tomatoes: from "poisonous" to popular

Historically, tomatoes were received with suspicion when first introduced to European markets and cuisine in the 16th century. Their bright and vibrant red color had associations with the forbidden fruit; the looks of the fruit were linked to toxic nightshade, and together with some lead poisoning incidents from pewter plates, fueled the belief that tomatoes were poisonous. Over time, improved cultivation techniques and shifting cultural perceptions transformed tomatoes into a beloved ingredient—especially in Mediterranean cuisine. Jordan details this dramatic transition in “The Heirloom Tomato as Cultural Object: Investigating Taste and Space,” reflecting how food narratives evolve with societal values and scientific insight.¹⁸

Mushrooms: sacred rituals vs. commodification

Mushrooms, especially the psilocybin varieties, hold a dual narrative. In Oaxaca, Mexico, they have long played a central role in sacred rituals and Indigenous healing practices. For centuries, Indigenous communities have revered these fungi, known as “niños santos” or “sacred children,” for their spiritual and medicinal properties. In contrast, in the West, there is a growing trend toward commodification. While they became banned in Mexico after colonization, the mushrooms entered the industry of the Netherlands and USA as entertainment products and tools to increase focus and productivity. Its demand has become promoted by pharmaceutical and scientific studies.¹⁹ This shift raises pressing concerns about cultural appropriation and the exploitation of Indigenous knowledge.

Together, these narratives emphasize that the cultural meanings of biomaterials are not static but evolve in response to broader economic, scientific, and societal influences. They remind us that while our food systems and their representations in media and technology may shift, they always carry deep historical and cultural legacies that warrant careful reflection.

METHODS AND ARTISTIC PROCESS

The AI images in Edible Notios were developed using LoRAs (Low-Rank Adaptation networks) from a Google Colab notebook to train the Stable Diffusion v1.5 LoRA model. This method allowed users to tailor the AI’s understanding of specific,

¹⁸ Jennifer Jordan, “The Heirloom Tomato as Cultural Object: Investigating Taste and Space,” *Sociologia Ruralis* 47, no. 1 (2007): 20–41, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9523.2007.00426.x>.

¹⁹ Robin L. Carhart-Harris et al., “The Therapeutic Potential of Psilocybin and the Growing Interest in Psychedelic Medicines,” *Neuropsychopharmacology* 42, no. 11 (2017): 2105–2113, <https://doi.org/10.1038/npp.2017.84>.

The new data sets were used together with textual prompts to create mosaics that are common ornaments in traditional Mexican kitchens after colonialism. The results bring up images where biomaterials—tomato, avocado, or mushroom—intertwine with imagery of arms and gunfire from narcotraffic, as well as shamanistic visuals reminiscent of the traditional use of mushrooms in Oaxaca or the medical gaze of pills from the pharmaceutical industry. The mixture challenges us to understand that for data prediction, a much more complex connection of thoughts, culture, and stories is necessary.

Figure 2: Diagram of prompting Methodology and example of mosaics generated with the datasets

This process was carried out using Automatic1111's Stable Diffusion software. The artist brought the generated LoRA in customised settings and used them to generate visual mosaics reminiscent of traditional Mexican kitchen tiles. For precision, we adjusted the sampling methods (Euler a, DPM++ 2M Karras), CFG scale (7—12), and denoising strength (0.4—0.7) to refine compositions. ControlNet and inpainting helped structure elements, ensuring coherence in blending organic and violent motifs. The results challenge AI's capacity to represent multilayered cultural narratives, urging a more nuanced approach to data-driven imagery.

The centrepiece of the installation is a dining experience featuring speculative dishes that represent complex narratives of selected biomaterials. This

culinary aspect serves as a metaphor for the mental and biological intake of thoughts with the data that populate AI networks. The materials selected for the non-edible dishes were greenware or unfired clay, biodegradable latex, and agar, considering that the materials could degrade and be transient. On the other hand, there were three edible options, one per narrative, and those were available to taste by the visitors.

Figure 3: Non-Edible Dish. Pasta with mushrooms made of unfired clay for the psilocybin representation

For Tomato narratives, we presented alginate bubbles with tomato juice inside, a red, vibrant gelatinous sphere to enhance the colour that gave it the fame of being poisonous, and we made it very small in contrast with the technological-driven growth of tomatoes demanding bigger and bigger fruits. The second edible dish was cubes of avocado and agar-agar gelatine with citrus powder and sugar to give a sour-sweet flavour of the duality of avocado between violence and delicatessen. The third dish was a figurine of a mushroom made with marzipan inside of a vegan capsule as medicine. Taking a pill is an invitation to change one's attitude toward the biomaterial and procure awareness of what narratives we feed into ourselves.

Figure 4. Spheres of calcium alginate with tomato juice

Figure 5. Installation, set up and audience interaction

This culinary aspect pretends to question what we consume and how narratives shape our perceptions of food and technology. Inspired by speculative design methodologies, the dishes are not meant to provide direct answers but to provoke reflection, encouraging participants to engage in an alternative way of knowing, blending sensory experience with critical inquiry. The act of designing, in this case, a new dish, can challenge existing assumptions and open up possibilities for exploring alternative ways of thinking and acting. This process fosters a deeper awareness of the contextual, political, and cultural forces that shape design practices. In turn, it encourages reflection on the potential consequences and

impacts of introducing new products and services into society.²¹

Figure 6. Diagram of speculative world configurations.²²

The previous diagram is a starting point for the speculative design process presented in the book *Beyond speculative design: past-present-future*. In *Edible Notions*, the “coordinates” (A) represent the individual, cultural, and technological dynamics shaping the data sets of AI. The artwork speculatively examines AI biases in food-related datasets, focusing on materials like avocados, tomatoes, and mushrooms. By extrapolating these biases, the work shapes a new narrative (B) that critiques how AI influences perspectives and history (C). The project “stretches” these coordinates, maintaining plausibility to provoke thoughtful reflection on the role of technology in shaping cultural narratives around food. Another important aspect of the methodology presented by Mitrović et al. is the use of tensions to generate the design. During this research, we tried to focus on the PARTICIPANT—WITNESS, and PROP—PRODUCT. The first tension addresses the level of engagement of the audience, ranging from detached observers to active participants. This tension raises questions about whether the public should be actively involved in the design process of AI or remain passive observers. The PROP—PRODUCT tension explores the role of the object in storytelling by having speculative dishes to support and structure a narrative by connecting fictional elements in the viewer's mind, or as a product, generating spontaneous stories

²¹ Ivica Mitrović, James Auger, Julian Hanna, and Ingi Helgason, eds., *Beyond Speculative Design: Past-Present - Future* (Split: University of Split, 2021), <https://speculativeedu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Beyond-Speculative-Design.pdf>.

²² Ivica Mitrović, James Auger, Julian Hanna, and Ingi Helgason, eds., *Beyond Speculative Design: Past-Present - Future* (Split: University of Split, 2021), <https://speculativeedu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Beyond-Speculative-Design.pdf>.

when interacted with by the user.²³

Complementary audios were presented to listen to while sitting next to the table, deepening the exploration of food audio narratives and inviting reflection on the biases embedded in them. These stories were made by recording humans reading the stories; two of them are in the same voice, but then the audio was passed through AI voice modification to increase variety in the voice timbre.

Figure 7. Installation of audio interaction

We presented other elements to reinforce the idea of different notions and mixtures. At the beginning of the journey in the gallery, there was a screen reacting to the observer's position. According to the viewpoint, the visitor will see one image of a tomato or another view of a speculative tomato moving and playing with their space position towards the screen.

A projection and audio were presented in front of the dinner table, inspired by dances and sounds from a typical family gathering of the artist. Videos of persons dancing salsa and merengue were modified with the newly created LoRA for the biomaterials, creating then a party of entities of the mixture. The songs were also generated by AI using a Suno subscription, where the artist input the lyrics inspired by the narratives and the style until the desired song was generated. The lyrics had a mixture of English, Spanish and Croatian languages for the context of creating the artwork and the difference in the semiotics of three different languages.

²³ Mitrović et al., *Beyond Speculative Design*, 94-163.

Figure 8. Installation of digital visual elements

The speculative dishes and digital elements work together to invite visitors to rethink what they know about food, culture, and technology. By transforming familiar ingredients into something unexpected, the installation highlights how our perceptions are shaped by history, industry, and the way stories are told. AI plays a key role in this process—not just as a tool but as a collaborator that reshapes voices, visuals, and even music. Sometimes, it enhances cultural narratives; other times, it distorts them, raising questions about authenticity and bias. The project encourages curiosity rather than giving direct answers, asking visitors to reflect on what stories—both human and machine-made—we choose to believe and share.

Figure 9. Installation setup

CONCLUSION

Through *Edible Notions*, I wanted to explore the intersection of AI, bias, and cultural narratives embedded in food biomaterials. The project challenged conventional AI dataset creation by introducing a methodology that acknowledges contrasting perspectives within the same object of study in a mixed and undisciplined approach. By integrating speculative dining experiences and AI-generated visuals, the installation invited visitors to reflect on the biases we feed to technology and accept for ourselves.

Our research intended to highlight that AI is not a neutral tool; it mirrors societal values, reinforcing dominant narratives while often marginalizing others. By engaging with theories from Haraway, Latour, Hui, and Kohn, I tried to examine the potential of AI as an active participant in knowledge production, emphasizing that AI technology should not only be an automation instrument but also a medium for critical engagement with cultural diversity. *Edible Notions* dealing with biomaterials—such as avocados, tomatoes, and mushrooms—carry historical and socio-political narratives that shift over time, influenced by colonial histories, economic forces, and scientific advancements.

While the project was successfully presented and marked the biases in AI datasets and cultural food narratives, some areas will be further developed for a stronger presentation: 1. Deeper Technological Analysis, for example, engaging directly with AI engineers or data ethicists could offer additional insights. 2. Modify the strategy for food consumption to highlight the forces of AI feeding our perspectives, instead of the visitor freely choosing to taste or not a dish the AI system will indicate what dish to engage with to bring the artwork to function. 3. Visitor Engagement with AI—Creating direct interactions between exhibition visitors and AI entities would provide empirical insights into how audiences perceive this relationship. This could guide future adaptations of the installation.

A curious note was the fear or caution by the audience to taste noncommunal presentation of the dishes in a gallery set up, Interestingly, this precaution is often underestimated when we receive information generated by the neural networks or what mental feeding we are accepting to build our perspectives of the world.

Finally, *Edible Notions* positions AI as a creative partner rather than a passive tool, questioning the narratives we embed in both technology and food. By unsettling the assumption of neutrality in AI-generated imagery, the project questions the necessity of situating technological development within specific cultural, historical, and ethical contexts. As we feed AI with datasets, we must ask: What perspectives are we nurturing, and which are left malnourished? Just as food shapes our bodies, the data we consume shapes our understanding of the world. The challenge remains: How do we cultivate a more inclusive, critical, and nuanced approach to AI and its role in shaping human perception? □

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